

PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR INTERPERSONAL RELATIONS THROUGH THE HERITAGE OF EASTERN THINKERS

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Abstract. *In the article, the heritage of Eastern thinkers, its scientific significance today, the problem of preparing future teachers for interpersonal relations through the heritage of Eastern thinkers, based on national tradition, culture, values, increasing the prestige of the teaching profession, developing interest in the pedagogic profession, new the current importance of developing interpersonal relationships among future teachers in accordance with the requirements of the era, teaching forms and models is discussed.*

Keywords: *eastern thinkers, interpersonal relationship, heritage of thinkers, national tradition, culture, value, forms of education, life skills.*

It is clear to everyone that the ideas of the great thinkers of the East in the field of pedagogy made an important contribution to world pedagogy. However, in the modern East, there was no demand for the pedagogical legacy of the medieval scientists-thinkers until the Central Asian republics gained independence. Only in recent years has the interest in this treasure of pedagogical thought revived somewhat. Pedagogical views of the thinkers represent the democratic direction in the pedagogical thinking of the Middle Ages: they had a great influence on the ideas about man, on the formation and improvement of the theory of education and training of the young generation and continue to do so.

To this day, their pedagogical ideas create a basis for the formation of ideas not only about a person and his education, but also about humanity, the formation of a well-rounded personality, and the requirements for a teacher.

Al-Khorazmi, Al-Farabi, Al-Biruni, Ibn Sina, Umar Khayyam, Saadi, Abdurrahman Jami, Alisher Nawai, Zahiriddin Babur, Balasaghun Yusuf, Mahmudhaji Behbudi, Abdullah Awlani, Kashqar Mahmud, Ahmad Yugnaki and others. while studying the pedagogical views of his thinkers, the great scientist-pedagogues philosophically thought about man, personality and interpersonal relations, education and training of the growing young generation, and emphasized work, knowledge, intelligence, art of speech and high moral qualities. it can be concluded that it was of great importance. They wanted to see a person who is fully developed, skillful and educated.

Pedagogical principles, instructions, advices and recommendations, requirements and recommendations of Eastern thinkers are of urgent importance and in demand today. Thus, the following pedagogical views of the great thinkers of the Middle Ages East are accepted as the basis for the training of pedagogic personnel in the system of the higher pedagogic school:

Al-Beruni expressed the following opinion about the teacher-student relationship in the educational process, providing them with quality knowledge, "... arming students with scientific factors, experience and observation, repetition and reporting, learning tells about the need to attach importance to friendly relations in teaching, to follow the principles of pedagogical direction (from close to far, from unknown to less known) during the course of the lesson...»

In his writings, Ibn Sina expressed his thoughts about raising a perfect person, "... the use of individual opportunities, his striving for perfection, life principles: to live not only for yourself, but also for others; creative approach to your work; it is necessary to have high moral qualities. In this case, the requirements for the teacher are: to know the child's nature, his soul, individuality, to see him as a human being, to believe in his capabilities and to reveal them; moderation, delicacy and sharpness in relations with the student; humanism and belief in raising a full-fledged person, and the main subject of education is morality. In education and upbringing, it is appropriate to use such methods and methods as conversation, advice, example, analysis, synthesis, generalization..." he writes.

At the same time, when organizing the general education process, the student should not be busy with the textbook at once; - go from light to heavy; pay attention to teaching as a team; - he wrote down his opinion about taking into account children's inclinations, interests, abilities, etc. in education.

Al-Khorazmi, one of the great scholars, wrote about the sufficient potential of the teacher in providing knowledge to the learner and satisfying his requirements for learning, and the main focus was: "...the independence of students and creative activity; observes factors and phenomena, their description and consistent explanation, etc.

The pedagogical ideas of Al-Farabi, the thinker-encyclopedist of the East, constitute the main content of his views on educating, teaching, and improving the individual's active role in solving social problems. Therefore, Farabi can be considered one of the founders of the advanced pedagogical thinking of the medieval Muslim East.

Thus, he divided philosophy into two parts - the theoretical and social structure, which covers physics, metaphysics, knowledge, logic, etc., the practical part, which covers the problems of the state, ethics, it deals with issues related to human behavior, upbringing and education. contained. It follows that some issues of didactics, psychological issues of upbringing and education are given in theoretical philosophy - in the department of human knowledge and cognitive abilities. Pedagogical ideas - ideas about education are widely covered in his practical philosophy.

He attached great importance to the formation of a person and his personality, especially spiritual and moral education. He identified various character traits and moral qualities - bravery, courage, friendliness, generosity, intelligence, honesty, etc., and considered them to be the result of personal education and self-education.

Thus, according to Farabi, education of intellectual and moral qualities of a person can be done in two ways: in the process of voluntary actions of a person who is voluntarily oriented and when forced by force. However, the goal remains the same - to form a perfect, virtuous person, that is, a person with high qualities that meets the requirements and tasks of an ideal society.

According to him, education and upbringing can be carried out in the family, in a virtuous society with the help of a teacher and a leader. His views on education are described in the treatises "Fazil Shahar", "The Foundations of Wisdom", and "Introduction to Logic".

Al-Farabi - all-round development and improvement of personality; to educate moral standards of behavior, positive and noble characteristics and qualities; formation of spiritual needs that determine the main characteristics of a person's character, his intellectual development.

Requirements for a teacher: phenomenal memory, logic, keen observation, love of knowledge, bright speech, justice and goodness. Pedagogical methods: persuasion, proof, discussion, dialectic-logical, clarity, etc.

Farabi considers man to be the most perfect and mature end of the world's development. Accordingly, he says in his works that it is necessary to educate a person. He notes that the issues of the expected goal→(result) from educational methods occupy the main place. His instructions are very close to the structural structure of the current education and training technology:

1. Educational goal → social need
2. Educational content → educational process
3. The result → is a receiver of education and a provider of education.

Al-Beruni, in his pedagogical works on education, armed students with scientific factors; experiment and observe, repeat and report; stated his views on the existence of teaching (from close to distant, from unknown to less known) and others.

Important methodological foundations of education in the works of Abu Rayhan Beruni:

- not to bore the students in the lesson (development of motivational and personal development situations, determining the structural structure of the students' learning activity);
- integrity and consistency in education (unity and integrity of the educational, educational and personal development tasks of the lesson);
- an interesting presentation of a new topic, mainly through visual presentation (choosing educational methods, determining the method of using educational tools)
- appropriateness of the conducted exercises to the children's age (ensure the sequence of raising the students' mastery level from a certain level to a higher level)
- increasing the complexity of each educational process from easy to difficult (choosing technological means of education in accordance with the age of the student)
- do not allow forced strain in teaching the child (not forced use of ped technology)

Muslikhiddin Saadiy recognized the importance of interpersonal relations in the educational process in his work, based on the following principles: active participation of the individual in the formation of knowledge; taking into account natural inclinations as necessary conditions for the development of abilities; systematicity and availability of knowledge, their practical application, connecting knowledge with life; development of mental abilities; the leading role of labor education.

Humanistic education in the pedagogical teaching of Abdurrahman Jami; special emphasis is placed on scientificity, systematicity and consistency, availability, connection with practice.

In the wisdom of Saadi Shirozi, in the correct establishment of interpersonal relations in the process of education and training: the active participation of the individual in the formation of knowledge; taking into account natural inclinations as necessary conditions for the development of abilities; availability and systematicity of knowledge, their practical application, connecting knowledge with life; development of mental abilities; it is stated that the basis of principles such as the leading role of labor education will give good results.

Al-Ghazali (1056/59-1111), one of the most famous philosophers of the East, paid great attention to the development of interpersonal relations through the prism of pedagogy. The scientist's four-volume collection "Resurrection of Religious Sciences" is devoted, in particular, to the development of human abilities, and the education of children with the aim of observational methods.

Al-Ghazali stressed the need to learn to behave at the table, to be simple in everyday life, and to exercise through physical exercises from a young age. If educators, especially. if parents follow certain pedagogical recommendations, the child's spirit will take the necessary form. The teacher receives the child from his parents and continues the traditions of family education.

There are more than 150 treatises of the Iranian philosopher Nasiruddin Tusi (1202-1273) on various ideas about education and upbringing. In his pedagogical works "Teaching wisdom", "Book of wisdom", "On educating students", "Advising the student on the way to study" and other pedagogical works, mental, aesthetic and physical education is combined. comments on the appropriateness of the flour are given.

According to Tusi, knowledge serves as a medicine that a person uses throughout his life. In order to obtain such medicines, it is necessary to clearly understand the purpose and method of obtaining knowledge.

Medieval pedagogic traditions show that in education, training and establishing interpersonal relations, by placing man at the center of the world, separating him from the world and contrasting his personal essence with the whole world, it is always positive results are not achieved.

In conclusion, it should be said that one of the important principles that serve to improve the quality of education is the reference to history, customs and traditions, in particular, the pedagogical heritage of Eastern thinkers, and its effective use. The relevant ideas and principles of using the scientific heritage of the great scientists and thinkers of the East in the modern practice of pedagogical personnel training were adopted. This will help future teachers acquire new professional skills and set a higher level of thinking.

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